

HARNESSING POLLINATOR DIVERSITY IN CUCURBIT CROP PRODUCTION IN TANZANIA

Empowering Farmers and Agroecosystems Through the Conservation of Bee Biodiversity

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Message to readers

Cucurbit crops like watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), squash (*Cucurbita pepo*) and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) (Figure 1) are vital to farming families across East Africa, especially in Tanzania. These crops not only provide healthy and nutritious food for households, but they are also a reliable source of income for many smallholder farmers. With their ability to grow in a range of environments and their popularity in local markets, cucurbits play an important role in strengthening food security and improving livelihoods across rural communities.

Figure 1. Overview of the three target crops of this research report: watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*, [left](#)), squash (*Cucurbita pepo*, [center](#)) and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*, [right](#)). Botanical illustrations were generated using AI tools (Pyxl.Pro/OpenAI) with original input prompts under the creative direction of NJ Vereecken/ULB, for educational and non-commercial purposes.

However, **successful cucurbit farming depends heavily on the work of pollinators** — especially bees — who transfer pollen between flowers, enabling the plants to produce fruits. Without healthy pollinator populations, harvests can shrink dramatically, directly affecting farmers' incomes and family well-being.

This guide is designed to help farmers, cooperatives, and NGOs better understand the essential link between bees and cucurbit production, and to show practical ways to protect and encourage pollinators for bigger, better and more sustained harvests. By actively promoting on-farm pollinator conservation, farmers can grow stronger harvests and a stronger future!

What is pollination?

Pollination is the natural process that allows plants to produce fruits and seeds. It happens when pollen — a powdery substance made by flowers — is moved from the male part of a flower (the *anther*) to the female part (the *stigma*). This transfer can happen in different ways, but without pollination, most of our crops would not be able to give us the fruits and vegetables we depend on every day.

There are two main ways plants get pollinated: **by the wind** and **by animals like insects**. Wind pollination is common in grasses, cereals (like maize), and some trees. The plants release very light pollen into the air, and the wind carries it to other plants. This method works well when plants grow close together in large fields, but it is not efficient for all crops. Animal pollination, on the other hand, happens when insects such as bees, butterflies, or even birds and bats carry pollen from one flower to another as they collect food. This is especially important for crops that have bigger, more complex flowers — like cultivated cucurbits — that simply cannot rely on the wind alone.

For cucurbit crops like watermelon, cucumber, and squash, insect pollination is therefore absolutely essential. Their flowers are large and heavy, and their pollen is heavy and sticky — it does not « float » in the air easily. Bees, and to a lesser extent other insects, are perfectly adapted to visit these flowers, transferring pollen as they move from male to female blooms. **Without insects doing this work, cucurbit fruits would be few, small, or misshaped, causing farmers to lose income and food.**

Interestingly, even though many bees are specialised in pollinating animal-pollinated crops, **some bee species also collect pollen from wind-pollinated plants.** In Tanzania, it has been observed that honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) and bees of the genus *Lipotriches* (in the family Halictidae) actively gather pollen from grasses and other wind-pollinated species. They do this regularly to supplement their diets (for honey bees) or throughout their life time as a specific adaptation to pollen collection from grasses (for *Lipotriches* bees). While this behaviour shows the adaptability of bees, it also reminds us that natural grasslands and diverse field borders are important habitats, providing bees with food throughout the year.

Understanding how pollination works — and how different plants and pollinators interact — **is the first step in protecting bees and ensuring strong harvests.** In the next sections, we will explore why cucurbits are particularly dependent on insect pollination and how farmers can help their natural pollination allies.

Why is cucurbit pollination so special?

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), squash (*Cucurbita pepo*), and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) are some of the most important fruit vegetables grown by farmers in Tanzania and across East Africa. These crops belong to the cucurbit family (Cucurbitaceae), and they share a very special feature: their flowers are **monoecious**, meaning that each plant produces **two types of flowers** — **male flowers** and **female flowers** — separately, but on the **same plant**.

The **male flowers** are responsible for producing pollen, but they cannot form fruits. The **female flowers**, on the other hand, have a small swollen base (the ovary) that will grow into a fruit after it is properly pollinated. For successful fruit production, pollen must move from a male flower to a female flower, usually across different flowers on the same or neighbouring plants. This unique flower structure makes these crops **completely dependent on insect pollinators** to carry out pollination between the flowers (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Cucurbit pollination by a diversity of bee species: male flowers produce large, heavy and sticky pollen grains not adapted to travel through the air and that need to be transferred by bees to a female flower of the same species in order to produce a fruit that will be ultimately harvested. Botanical illustrations generated using AI tools (Pyxl.Pro/OpenAI) with original input prompts under the creative direction of NJ Vereecken/ULB, for educational and non-commercial purposes. All bee photos © NJ Vereecken.

It is also important to note that **flowering patterns in cucurbits are highly dynamic**. Male flowers often appear earlier and in greater numbers than female flowers, especially at the beginning of the flowering season. This means that farmers observing many flowers but few fruits early on should not be alarmed — it is part of the natural process. However, ensuring a healthy population of pollinators during the full flowering period is critical for a successful harvest of watermelon, squash, and cucumber.

By **understanding the special pollination needs of these three crops**, farmers and farming organisations can better appreciate the vital role of pollinators ([Figure 3](#)) and why protecting and encouraging them directly through tailored and more general ecological infrastructures (micro-habitats, flowering plants, nesting sites, etc.) can translate into stronger yields and higher incomes.

What makes cucurbit pollination particularly special is the **narrow window of time** in which flowers are receptive and able to set fruit. Both male and female flowers of cucurbits typically **open early in the morning and remain receptive for only a few hours**. If pollination does not occur during this short period, the flower will wither without producing fruit. In addition, cucurbit flowers require a **relatively high amount of pollen**—often several hundred pollen grains must be deposited on the stigma to ensure full fertilisation and well-formed fruits. This means that successful pollination not only depends on the presence of pollinators but also on their **timing, activity levels, and flower-to-flower movement**. As a result, cucurbit crops place a **greater demand on pollinator effectiveness** than many other field crops, making every morning of the flowering period a critical moment for fruit set and yield potential.

Figure 3. A female *Xylocopa nigrita* (Apidae) visiting a male flower of squash (*Cucurbita pepo*) for the collection of pollen grains ([left](#): Photo © O Ihsane) and a female hoverfly (Diptera, Syrphidae), another group of flower-visiting insects bearing a superficial resemblance to bees and often found in agroecosystems ([right](#): Photo © NJ Vereecken).

The economic importance of bee pollination in cucurbit production

Pollination is not just a natural process — it is an economic engine for farming families. In cucurbit crops like watermelon, squash, and cucumber, successful pollination by bees makes the difference between a poor harvest and a profitable one. Without pollinators, fruit set rates drop dramatically, resulting in fewer fruits, smaller fruits, and fruits with poor shapes that fetch lower prices at market. Some estimates indicate that over 80 to 100% of cucurbit fruits depend on insect pollination!

Studies around the world — and observations in Tanzania — show that cucurbit crops depend **almost entirely** on insect pollination. In fields where bees are abundant and active, farmers consistently report **higher fruit yields, better fruit quality**, and greater income (Figure 4).

Pollination impacts the **size and weight of fruits**. For example, a well-pollinated watermelon will not only be larger but will also have a better internal structure (more seeds evenly distributed, better flesh development) — qualities that buyers prefer and are willing to pay more for. Better pollination means more fruits **per plant** and **more kilograms per hectare**, translating directly to improved farm revenues

In Tanzania, **cucurbit farming is an important source of income**, particularly for smallholder farmers and women's groups. Investing in practices that support bees — like maintaining flowering borders, planting diverse crops, and minimising harmful pesticide use — is a smart economic strategy. Every flower visited by a bee is an opportunity for a bigger and better harvest.

Figure 4. Good pollination of cucurbit crops brought about by healthy bee populations and communities will result in larger fruits fetching higher market prices (left) as opposed to a situation where pollinators are considerably less abundant and less diverse (right). Botanical illustrations generated using AI tools (Pyxl.Pro/OpenAI) with original input prompts under the creative direction of NJ Vereecken/ULB, for educational and non-commercial purposes.

Meet the heroes of cucurbit pollination

Not all bees are the same — and that's good news for cucurbit farmers!

Different types of bees have different shapes, sizes, and behaviours, and each one plays a special role in helping crops like watermelon, squash, and cucumber produce healthy, market-ready fruits. Some bees are small and fast, visiting many flowers quickly. Others are larger and stronger, perfect for carrying heavy loads of sticky pollen between the big male and female flowers of cucurbits. This diversity of bees makes pollination more efficient, because different bees are active at different times of day, prefer different flowers, and use different foraging strategies. Having **many types of bees** on your farm is always a more resilient approach than relying on just one kind, namely the Western Honey Bee (*Apis mellifera*)!

In cucurbit farming, the best results come when a variety of wild bees and managed bees are present. Our results show that some bees, like honey bees (*Apis mellifera*), are famous helpers because they are present in high numbers at the cucurbit flowers (Figure 5). Others, like *Dactylurina* and *Braunsapis* species, are smaller wild bees that are fast and can be effective in pollinating the delicate cucurbit flowers.

Figure 5. Overview of the bee genera observed as flower visitors of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), squash (*Cucurbita pepo*) and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) in Morogoro, Tanzania. The results show that workers of the honey bee, *Apis mellifera*, vastly outnumbered wild bee species at our study sites. Adapted from Ihsane *et al.* (unpublished data).

The 10 bee genera you should know

Apis mellifera, the Western Honey Bee

Morphology: Medium-sized bees, 9–12 mm in length and with hairy eyes and a moderately hairy body. Honey bee workers are brown to dark brown in colour with lighter, yellowish to orange bands on the abdomen. They vary in colour depending on subspecies: the East African Lowland Honey Bee (*Apis mellifera scutellata*) is an orange-and-black coloured bee typically seen in grassland, bush, coastal, and forest areas. The East African Highland Honey Bee (*Apis mellifera monticola*) is the darker, chocolate-coloured subspecies adapted to higher altitude habitats (Figure 6).

Ecology: Social species and the only domesticated species recorded; lives in large colonies with a queen, workers, and drones. Highly generalist and adaptable, visiting a wide variety of flowers. Often domesticated and kept in hives for honey production.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: The Western honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) is one of the most widespread and well-known pollinators globally — and it plays an obvious role in cucurbit fields across Tanzania. Its social structure, large colony size, and high foraging activity make it an efficient and accessible pollinator for many crops, including watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), squash (*Cucurbita pepo*), and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*). However, *A. mellifera* is a super generalist forager and may not always be the most efficient cucurbit pollinator. Studies and field observations show that honey bees sometimes prefer other flowering plants nearby, especially if cucurbit flowers are less rewarding or fewer in number. Still, their high numbers and adaptability make *A. mellifera* a valuable contributor, especially when supported by diverse wild bee populations. With almost 2,000 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, this was the most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits (Figure 5).

Figure 6. General habitus of the Western Honey Bee (*Apis mellifera*, family Apidae, tribe Apini) with examples of colour variation on the abdomen, ranging from orange-and-black (left: Photo © A Pauly) to darker, chocolate-coloured specimens (right: Photo © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Dactylurina*, the Slender Stingless Bees

Morphology: Medium-sized bees, 5–8 mm in length and without hairs on their black body. Workers of *Dactylurina* have a slender, long and laterally compressed abdomen and their legs are hanging downwards when they are in flight ([Figure 7](#)).

Ecology: Social species; lives in large colonies with a queen, workers, and drones. Highly generalist and adaptable, visiting a wide variety of flowers. These are the only stingless bees (family Apidae, tribe Meliponini) establishing their colonies in exposed nests that hang on tree branches and that are covered in batumen lining, a hard brownish mixture of propolis and other plant materials. The function of this material is to protect the nest from the external environment.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: According to a recent study evaluating stingless bees as watermelon pollinators, *Dactylurina schmidtii* demonstrated the longest probing time on female watermelon flowers — spending an average of over 140 seconds per flower visit, much longer than any other species tested. Importantly, the pollination effectiveness of *D. schmidtii* improved significantly with multiple visits. After six or more visits, the amount and distribution of pollen approached the optimal range needed for successful fruit set in watermelon. In these cases, *D. schmidtii* achieved a similar level of effectiveness as the Western Honey Bee, *A. mellifera*, particularly in ensuring symmetrical fruit development through even pollen deposition. With 430 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, this was the second most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits ([Figure 5](#)).

Figure 7. Workers of *Dactylurina schmidtii* (family Apidae, tribe Meliponini) on a cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) flower ([top left](#): Photo © O Ihsane), general habitus showing the slender, long and laterally compressed abdomen ([top right](#) and [bottom](#): Photos © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Braunsapis*, the Black Reed Bees

Morphology: Small-sized bees, 4–7 mm in length, usually black and shiny with slightly greenish eyes, they appear almost hairless although fine hairs may be present on their legs and thorax. Most species display a spear-like ivory mark on their face, particularly in the female sex. They exhibit a relatively ventrally compressed abdomen ([Figure 8](#)).

Ecology: *Braunsapis* is the largest genus of the tribe Allodapini (family Apidae) and it is known for its array of social behaviours, from solitary species to others with more social interactions among nesting females. They nest in hollow plant stems, twigs, or reeds, which gives them the common name “Reed Bees.” These bees are generalist foragers, visiting a wide range of floral species throughout the day. Their preference for sunlit, open habitats makes them frequent visitors to field-edge vegetation.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: *Braunsapis* bees are among the most frequently observed visitors to cucurbit flowers in East African farming systems. Their small size and agility allow them to make rapid, repeated visits to both male and female flowers, especially in the morning when cucurbit flowers are most receptive. Although individual *Braunsapis* bees may deposit fewer pollen grains per visit compared to larger bees, their high foraging frequency and flower fidelity result in effective pollination over time. With 174 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, this was the third most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits ([Figure 5](#)).

Figure 8. Female of *Braunsapis* (family Apidae, tribe Allodapini) on a watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) flower ([top left](#): Photo © O Ihsane), and the general habitus showing the slightly ventrally compressed abdomen with sometimes sparse bands of whitish hairs and the spear-shaped ivory mark on the face ([top right](#): Photo © A Pauly; [bottom left](#) and [bottom right](#): Photos © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Plebeina*, the Termite Stingless Bees

Morphology: Small-sized bees, 3.5–6 mm in length, abdomen relatively short and triangular in cross-section, black to orange in colour. Workers exhibit greenish to greyish eyes, yellow maculation on the lower edge of their face, and dense snow whitish hairs on the sides of their thorax ([Figure 9](#)).

Ecology: Social species; lives in large colonies with a queen, workers, and drones. Highly generalist and adaptable, visiting a wide variety of flowers. This species establishes its colonies in cavities within active terrestrial termite nests. Colonies perform relatively poorly when kept in wooden nests for meliponiculture (i.e., beekeeping with stingless bees) — alternative designs using clay pots partly buried underground seem to be more suitable to keep them near households.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: *Plebeina* bees are frequently observed floral visitors in agroecosystems and in urban gardens. Their small size and agility allow them to make rapid, repeated visits to both male and female flowers, especially in the morning when cucurbit flowers are most receptive. With 114 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, this was the fourth most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits ([Figure 5](#)).

Figure 9. Workers of *Plebeina armata* (family Apidae, tribe Meliponini) habitus showing the red and black colour morphs ([top left](#) and [top right](#), respectively) with their hind legs loaded with yellow pollen. This stingless bee species establishes its colonies in cavities within active terrestrial termite nests ([bottom](#)) (Photos © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Ceratina*, the Small Carpenter Bees

Morphology: Small-sized bees, 3–7 mm in length, abdomen generally longer than the wing length. Males and females of *Ceratina* are characterised by a smooth, shiny cuticle — many species also exhibit a metallic sheen, ranging from black to blue-green to bronze, especially on the thorax and abdomen. Their bodies are covered in deep and large punctuations, with sparse hairs on the legs and narrow hair bands on the abdomen. Their wings are sometimes slightly opaque and black ([Figure 10](#)).

Ecology: *Ceratina* are solitary bees, though some species may exhibit semi-social behavior, especially in overlapping generations. They typically nest inside soft or pithy plant stems, such as dead twigs, grass stalks, or dry stems — which gives them the name “Small Carpenter Bees.” Their nests are linear tunnels with compartments for brood cells. *Ceratina* are generalist foragers, active throughout the day, and commonly found in semi-natural field edges, gardens, and fallow areas with diverse flowering plant communities.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: *Ceratina* bees are frequently observed floral visitors in agroecosystems and in urban gardens. Their small size and agility allow them to make rapid, repeated visits to both male and female flowers, especially in the morning when cucurbit flowers are most receptive. With 57 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, these were the fifth most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits ([Figure 5](#)).

Figure 10. General habitus of a *Ceratina* sp. male ([top left](#)) and female ([bottom left](#)) (family Apidae, tribe Ceratinini) displaying a characteristic metallic, shiny cuticle with large and deep punctuations — often appearing bronze or blue/green under sunlight — in different species (Photos © NJ Vereecken). The most common species collected during our surveys, *Ceratina* cf. *tanganyicensis* ([right](#)), is metallic black, sports ivory marks on the front legs, and exhibits a sparse punctation pattern on the central region of the thorax (Photo © A Pauly).

Genus *Xylocopa*, the Large Carpenter Bees

Morphology: Large-sized bees, 15–25 mm in length, making them the largest native bees observed in East Africa. They have a black, shiny body, often with a metallic bluish or purplish tint. Their thorax and abdomen often exhibit dense patches of black, yellow, orange or even white hairs. Their wings are broad and dark-tinted, sometimes showing iridescent reflections ([Figure 11](#)).

Ecology: *Xylocopa* bees (family Apidae, tribe Xylocopini) are typically solitary, though some species may share nesting tunnels (facultative sociality). They excavate their nests in dead wood, bamboo, or dry wooden structures, earning them the name “Large Carpenter Bees.” Females chew almost perfectly round holes into soft or decaying wood to create linear tunnels where they lay eggs in separate brood cells. They are generalist foragers sometimes with preferences for certain plant families and they are capable of flying long distances. They are more common in open woodlands, agroforestry zones, and field margins where nesting wood is available.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: Despite their solitary behaviour, *Xylocopa* bees are effective pollinators of cucurbit crops due to their large body size and ability to carry and transfer large amounts of pollen between foraging bouts. Although less frequent than smaller bees (see genera above), each visit by *Xylocopa* can result in significant pollen deposition. With 50 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, these were the sixth most common bee species recorded on cucurbits ([Figure 5](#)).

Figure 11. Female *Xylocopa nigrita* (family Apidae, tribe Xylocopini) on a squash (*Cucurbita pepo*) flower ([top left](#)) (Photo © O Ihsane) and general habitus of *X. caffra*, a common visitor of flowering crops ([top right](#)) (Photo © A Pauly). Large Carpenter Bees typically nest in dead wood where they lay eggs in separate brood cells ([bottom](#)) (Photo © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Macrogalea*, the Large Reed Bees

Morphology: Medium-sized bees, 8–11 mm in length, the only large, hairy, robust bees in the tribe Allodapini (family Apidae, see also the genus *Braunsapis* described above). The forewing is generally much shorter than the abdomen and in the female sex, the lower part of the face (clypeus) bears a distinctive whitish longitudinal band in its middle section. They exhibit a relatively ventrally compressed abdomen like other Reed Bees (Figure 12). *Macrogalea* males are exceedingly rarely observed and collected in the field, and they are characterised by their enlarged eyes, very short antennae, and very long, dense, erect hair on the clypeus. There are four East African species recorded, including one that has evolved a parasitic behaviour (brood parasite) on another *Macrogalea* species.

Ecology: They are stem-nesting bees, often using dead reed stems, hollow grasses, or plant stalks to construct their brood chambers with a preference for in vertical burrows in pithy stems. They are generalist foragers sometimes with preferences for certain plant families, including Asteraceae, Convolvulaceae, Cucurbitaceae and Malvaceae: they seem particularly well adapted to the collection of pollen from flowering plants producing large sized pollen grains. They can be very common locally, including in highly disturbed areas close to villages and cities, as well as in open woodlands, agroforestry zones, and field margins where their preferred nesting sites are available.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: Despite their solitary nature, *Macrogalea* bees are effective pollinators of cucurbit crops due to their foraging flexibility and their ability to carry and transfer large amounts of pollen between foraging bouts. Although less frequent than other Reed Bees and Stingless Bees listed above. With 41 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, these were the seventh most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits (Figure 5) and they are also reported as important pollinators of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*, in the plant family Malvaceae, also known as gombo or lady's fingers).

Figure 12. Female *Macrogalea candida* (family Apidae, tribe Allodapini) on a squash (*Cucurbita pepo*) flower (left) and general habitus of the same species showing the whitish longitudinal band on the middle section of its face (clypeus), the fulvous hairs on the pollen-collecting brush of hairs located on its hind legs (scopa) and its pointed abdomen (Photos © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Lasioglossum*, the Sweat Bees

Morphology: *Lasioglossum* bees vary in size, generally 5–9 mm in length, with slender bodies. They are often discreet and easily overlooked in the field due to their small size and inconspicuous appearance, and their diagnostic features such as the shape of their hind tibial spur (calcar) or that of their carina on the back of their thorax (propodeum), as well as the length of their tongue (glossa) are subtle and often difficult to observe without expert knowledge or the use of a stereomicroscope. The marked strength of their wing veins is also characteristic in subgenera like *Ipomalictus* and *Ctenonomia*: those towards the apex on the forewings are distinctly fainter than those closer to the wing base. Most species are dark-coloured, often black and have short, fine hairs primarily on the thorax and hind legs, with more or less conspicuous hair bands on their abdomen (Figure 13).

Ecology: *Lasioglossum* species belong to the family Halictidae and they are among the most diverse and widespread bee genera worldwide, occupying a wide range of habitats, including croplands, grasslands, and disturbed areas. Most are ground-nesting, building shallow burrows in bare or lightly vegetated soil. Some species are solitary, while others show communal or semi-social behavior. Subgenera like *Ipomalictus* and *Ctenonomia* are especially common in open agricultural landscapes, including cucurbit fields. Their foraging patterns are somewhat contrasted, with *Ipomalictus* species exhibiting a specialisation on the collection of pollen from plants in the families Convolvulaceae, Malvaceae and Cucurbitaceae, i.e. plants that usually produce larger pollen grains. By contrast, most species of *Ctenonomia* are reported to be pollen generalists.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: *Lasioglossum* bees, in particular species from the *Ipomalictus* and *Ctenonomia* subgenera, are important contributors to cucurbit pollination in Tanzanian agroecosystems. With 40 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, these were almost as frequent as *Macrogalea* bees, and the eighth most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits (Figure 5).

Figure 13. Female *Lasioglossum (Ipomalictus)* sp. (family Halictidae) covered in cucurbit pollen (note the large size of pollen grains) (left) and general habitus of a female *Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) entebbianum* (Photos © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Hypotrigona*, the Dwarf Stingless Bees

Morphology: *Hypotrigona* are among the smallest bees in Africa, typically measuring just 2–4 mm in length. Their bodies are slender, dark brown to black, and appear almost hairless to the naked eye. Due to their tiny size, they resemble small flying ants or gnats in the field and are easily overlooked (Figure 14). The term “dwarf” highlights this extreme small size, a feature shared with another group of tiny African endemic stingless bees in the genus *Liotrigona*.

Ecology: *Hypotrigona* (family Apidae, tribe Meliponini) are highly social stingless bees, living in permanent colonies with a queen and several hundreds of active workers. They often nest in small cavities in tree bark, cracks in walls (including in or around houses), or even abandoned insect burrows, using a mix of wax and plant resin to build their entrance tubes and nest structure. These bees are remarkably adaptable to urban, peri-urban, and rural environments. Their colonies are small compared to those of other stingless bees like *Dactylurina*, but they are exceptionally active and persistent foragers, often flying under cloudy conditions or low light.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: *Hypotrigona* bees, despite their tiny size, have proven to be active and competent pollinators of cucurbit crops, particularly watermelon and cucumber. Recent studies in Kenya demonstrated that *H. gribodoi* consistently visited female watermelon and cucumber flowers and deposited pollen, although in smaller quantities per visit compared to larger bees. On average, *H. gribodoi* spent about 50 seconds per visit, significantly more than the honey bee, *Apis mellifera scutellata*, but less than *Dactylurina schmidtii*, suggesting moderate probing effort. Importantly, the study showed that while *H. gribodoi* deposited fewer pollen grains during a single visit of watermelon flowers, the total pollen deposition increased significantly with multiple visits. With 35 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, these were nearly as frequent as *Macrogalea* and *Lasioglossum* bees, and the ninth most common bee species we recorded on cucurbits (Figure 5).

Figure 14. Worker of *Hypotrigona* sp. (Apidae, tribe Meliponini) visiting a watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) flower (left) (Photo © O Ihsane) and its general habitus showing the diagnostic rounded upper apical part of its hind tibia (right) (Photo © NJ Vereecken).

Genus *Trinomia*, the Three-Toothed Nomiine Bees

Morphology: *Trinomia* are medium-sized bees within the subfamily Nomiinae, generally measuring 7–10 mm in length. Males are characterised by a distinctive apical process on the hind tibia and a swollen hind femur bearing three ventrally directed spines, which inspired the genus name. While nomiine bees in many other genera have similar traits, this 3-spined femur configuration is particularly diagnostic for species in the genus *Trinomia*. Females lack these diagnostic spines, but they share the genus's entirely carinate basitibial plate, a particular feature on their « knees » visible on their hind legs. Females also exhibit a dull, honeycomb-like surface punctation on the dorsal surface of the first abdominal segment (tergum 1 or T1), which resembles a hexagonal pattern. These arguably subtle features are difficult to discern in the field, they require building up some experience in bee morphological examination, but they are reliable and diagnostic under microscopic observation (Figure 15).

Ecology: Species of *Trinomia* are presumed to be ground-nesting, as are other Nomiine bees (family Halictidae, subfamily Nomiinae), although no nest has been formally described for this genus. *Trinomia* bees are thought to be generalist foragers, collecting pollen from a wide variety of flowering plant families. Despite their wide distribution, most occurrence records come from just a few species, notably *T. tridentata* and *T. orientalis*. These bees are typically found in open habitats and savanna landscapes, and they may be under-sampled due to their cryptic appearance and subtle diagnostic traits.

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: Although much less frequently recorded in the field than some other genera of bees described above, *Trinomia* bees have been observed foraging on cucurbit flowers in Tanzania and are active pollen carriers, particularly in lowland farming systems. Their medium body size allows them to make direct contact with both anthers and stigmas, presumably supporting effective pollen transfer. With only 13 flower visits recorded during our field surveys, these were some of the least frequent bee species we recorded on cucurbits (Figure 5).

Figure 15. Male of *Trinomia orientalis* (Halictidae, subfamily Nomiinae) exhibiting the swollen hind femur bearing three ventrally directed spines (left: Photo © NJ Vereecken) and general habitus of a female *T. orientalis* (right: Photo © A Pauly).

Hoverflies visit cucurbit flowers, too!

Ecology: Syrphid flies (Diptera, Syrphidae) are frequent and effective visitors to a wide variety of wild flowering plants and cultivated crops. Beyond their role as pollinators, the larvae of many syrphid species are well-known predators of agricultural pests such as aphids and leafhoppers, and also important decomposers of organic matter, aiding in nutrient cycling within agroecosystems. These dual roles as both pollinators and natural enemies underscore the ecological and agricultural importance of hoverflies in sustainable farming and biological control programs.

Morphology: Hoverflies or syrphid flies are frequently mistaken for bees or wasps due to their bright yellow or brown stripes. As members of the order *Diptera*, syrphid flies are easily distinguished from bees and wasps by possessing only a single pair of wings. In the Morogoro region, at least 55 species of Syrphidae have been recorded visiting flowers of cucurbit crops, with a total of 12,969 individual observations. The most commonly encountered species include *Toxomerus floralis* (Figure 16), but also native species like *Paragus borbonicus*, and *Ischiodon aegyptius*, which account for 51.3%, 10.2%, and 6.6% of all Syrphidae records in the region, respectively (Kabota et al., 2025).

Relevance for cucurbit pollination: Syrphid flies are often considered the second-most important group of pollinators after wild bees. Bees are thought to be able to carry a greater volume of pollen on their bodies, but flies may be able to compensate for this by making a greater number of flower visits. Augmentative releases of laboratory-reared hoverflies have proven to enhance melon fruit set by 100% in greenhouses (Li et al., 2023). Additional field studies are required to estimate their potential as pollinators of cucurbit crops.

Figure 16. The non-native hoverfly *Toxomerus floralis* (Diptera, Syrphidae) was the most common hoverfly recorded on cucurbits during our field surveys (left: Photo © J Visser); several other native hoverfly species visited cucurbit flowers too (right: Photo © A Pauly).

How can we protect our pollinators?

Pollinators are not just helpers in the field—they are **essential allies in cucurbit production**. From watermelon and squash to cucumber, these crops rely heavily on insect pollinators to transfer pollen between their male and female flowers. Yet, these pollinators are poorly known, primarily due to a lack of field studies documenting their diversity, and how their communities change with crop species, cropping season on environmental variables such as the altitude or the climate zones (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Field surveys on cucurbit pollinators provide essential insights into the role of wild and managed insects in supporting fruit and seed production. By documenting which bee species visit cucurbit flowers, such studies help farmers, practitioners and policymakers better understand the dependence of agricultural systems on biodiversity (Photos © NJ Vereecken).

Tailored strategies for cucurbit farming

To effectively conserve pollinators in cucurbit agroecosystems, farmers and NGOs should prioritise actions that reflect the biology and behavior of bees like *Dactylurina*, *Lipotriches*, *Plebeina*, *Ceratina*, and others. These include (but are not limited to):

- **Preserving trees, flowering hedgerows and semi-natural habitats** near fields to provide nectar and pollen outside of cucurbit blooming periods;
- **Avoiding deep soil tillage and plowing near field margins**, which can destroy the nests of ground-nesting genera such as *Lasioglossum*, *Trinomia*, and *Lipotriches*;
- **Leaving some dry stems or pithy twigs**, including in frequently cut hedgerows, which serve as nesting sites for *Ceratina* and *Macrogalea*;
- **Installing small wooden bee boxes or logs**, which can be colonised by *Xylocopa* species near households or close to the agricultural plots.

A note on pesticide use in cucurbit farming

Despite growing interest in more sustainable agricultural practices, the use of chemical pesticides remains widespread in cucurbit farming. These inputs are often applied routinely as a preventive measure, even when pest or disease pressure is low.

However, research and field observations increasingly point to **negative impacts on wildlife**—including beneficial insects like pollinators—and **potential risks to human health**, particularly through exposure to pesticides on food and in the environment. This highlights the urgent need to rethink crop protection strategies in a way that balances productivity with ecological and public health.

Several pesticides are readily available to cucurbit farmers and their use is still prevalent in Tanzanian cucurbit fields: **“Masterkinga 72 WP” (Mancozeb + Cymoxanil)** and **“Chloro Force” (Chlorothalonil)**. These are both **broad-spectrum fungicides** (Figure 18) that have several documented impacts on bee health:

Chlorothalonil, though not highly toxic in the short term to adult bees, has been shown to:

- **Increase larval mortality** and reduce body size and gland development;
- **Alter the gut microbiome**, making bees more vulnerable to disease;
- **Reduce nutrition and survival** of foragers and newly emerged adults.

Figure 18. Containers of broad-spectrum fungicides left in cucurbit fields. “Chloro Force” (Chlorothalonil) and “Masterkinga 72 WP” (Mancozeb + Cymoxanil) are used to control fungal infections of cucurbits, but a growing number of studies have shown that fungicides can also harm pollinators, especially when applied during flowering (Photos © NJ Vereecken).

Mancozeb, in turn, is among the most concerning fungicides:

- It has **insecticidal properties** and has been reported to **reduce soil biodiversity**, affecting the nesting habitat of ground-nesting pollinators;
- Studies show genetic effects in plant cells (e.g., onions) and **toxicity to non-target flowering plants** such as marigolds at recommended doses;
- It significantly reduced **larval weight and microbial diversity** in solitary bees in recent laboratory trials.

Given these findings, **routine fungicide use during bloom**, especially in cucurbits that depend entirely on insect pollination, **poses a hidden but substantial threat** to both managed and wild bee populations.

Towards more sustainable agricultural practices in cucurbit farming

To sustain both **crop health** and **pollination services** in cucurbit farming, there is a clear need to move beyond conventional pesticide-driven approaches toward more ecologically balanced strategies. **Integrated Pest and Pollinator Management (IPPM)** offers a practical framework for achieving this balance by integrating pest control methods with pollinator conservation objectives. Unlike traditional Integrated Pest Management (IPM), IPPM explicitly recognises that **pollinators are part of the agricultural system's functional biodiversity**—not just auxiliary actors.

In cucurbit systems, IPPM means combining **regular pest monitoring, threshold-based pesticide application**, and the use of **biological controls** with proactive measures to **support wild and managed pollinators**. These include conserving field-edge habitats, planting flowering resources outside of the main crop bloom, reducing tillage to protect ground-nesting bees, and avoiding pesticide sprays during peak foraging hours. Farmers can also diversify their crops and rotate cucurbits with non-host species to minimise pest buildup while maintaining landscape heterogeneity that supports pollinator foraging.

This approach aligns closely with the principles of **agroecology**, which emphasises working with and not against natural processes, reducing dependency on external inputs, and restoring ecological balance in production systems. In cucurbit farming, agroecological practices can amplify IPPM benefits by enhancing **soil health**, reducing **fungal disease pressure** through improved crop rotation, and fostering **pollinator-rich environments** through mixed cropping or the use of living ground covers. Ultimately, IPPM serves as a **bridge between agronomic performance and ecological sustainability**, enabling farmers to maintain yields and income while securing the pollination services upon which cucurbit production fundamentally depends.

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